

A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW AND META-ANALYSIS OF DENTAL IMPLANTS IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS

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Abstract

This review aimed to assess the effects of diabetes mellitus on dental implant failure rates and marginal bone loss (MBL). An electronic search was conducted across three databases, supplemented by a manual search of relevant journals. Meta-analyses and meta-regressions were performed to examine how the odds ratio (OR) and MBL were influenced by follow-up duration. A total of 89 studies were included in the review, encompassing 5,510 implants in diabetic patients and 62,780 in non-diabetic patients. Pairwise meta-analysis revealed a higher failure risk for implants in diabetic patients compared to non-diabetic patients (OR 1.777, $p < 0.001$). Implant failure was significantly more frequent in type 1 diabetes patients than in type 2 (OR 4.477, $p = 0.032$). Statistically significant differences in implant failure rates were observed between the maxilla and mandible, with significance only in the maxilla. The mean difference (MD) in MBL between diabetic and non-diabetic patients was 0.776 mm ($p = 0.027$), with an estimated MBL MD increase of 0.032 mm per additional month of follow-up ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, there was an estimated OR decrease of 0.007 for each extra month of follow-up ($p = 0.048$). In conclusion, dental implants in diabetic patients showed a 77.7% higher failure risk compared to those in non-diabetic patients.

Keywords: dental implant, implant failure, marginal bone loss, diabetes mellitus, systematic review, meta-analysis, meta-regression.

1. Introduction

Diabetes mellitus encompasses a group of metabolic disorders marked by elevated blood glucose levels, which arise from problems in insulin production (when the pancreas does not release enough insulin), insulin function (when the body cannot effectively utilize the insulin produced), or both. The most common form, type 2 diabetes, represents the vast majority of cases worldwide, and its prevalence has been rapidly increasing, with predictions indicating a significant rise in affected adults over the coming years. This highlights the critical importance of understanding the impacts of diabetes.

Chronic high blood sugar levels in diabetes often lead to damage, dysfunction, or even failure of various tissues and organs, resulting in significant health burdens. Additionally, the duration of diabetes itself can influence a patient's clinical and functional condition, regardless of glycemic control or age. These complications stem from several adverse effects, such as delayed wound healing, microvascular issues, reduced infection response, and compromised bone metabolism and strength. For individuals who develop type 2 diabetes at a young age, the risk of these complications steadily increases over time, affecting many by early adulthood.

Blood sugar levels, or glycemia, play an important role in these outcomes, as research has shown a connection between glycemic control and the development of complications affecting both small and large blood vessels. Intensive glycemic control in diabetic patients can delay the onset and progression of various complications linked to microvascular damage,

although this benefit tends to diminish once complications have already manifested. Diabetic patients are considered to have controlled diabetes when their blood glucose levels are kept close to normal, typically indicated by the HbA1c test, which measures the percentage of glycated hemoglobin. Patients with HbA1c levels up to a certain threshold are considered well-controlled.

The negative impact of diabetes on bone metabolism has led to concerns about the long-term success of dental implants in diabetic patients. A prior systematic review on this topic has provided some insight, suggesting that diabetes may indeed affect implant failure rates compared to non-diabetic patients. However, that earlier review included only a limited number of studies. Therefore, the goal of this current systematic review is to expand on previous findings, comparing implant failure rates and marginal bone loss between diabetic and non-diabetic patients on a larger scale.

2. Materials and Methods

This study adhered to the guidelines set forth by the PRISMA 2020 Statement and was registered in the PROSPERO database (CRD42021240670).

2.1. Objective

The aim of this study was to evaluate the null hypothesis that no difference exists in implant failure rates and marginal bone loss (MBL) following the placement of dental implants in diabetic patients compared to non-diabetic patients, contrasting this with the alternative hypothesis that a difference does exist. This investigation was conducted through a systematic review of the literature.

To guide the study, the PICO framework (participants, interventions, comparisons, outcomes) was used to formulate the focused question: Among partially and fully edentulous patients (participants) receiving dental implants (intervention), is there a difference in implant failure rates and MBL (outcomes) between diabetic and non-diabetic patients (comparison)?

2.2. Search Strategies

An electronic search without date restrictions was conducted, with the final update completed in October 2023, across the following databases: PubMed/Medline, Web of Science, and Scopus. The search terms used were: (“dental implant” OR “oral implant”) AND (diabetes OR diabetic)

A manual search of journals related to dental implants (listed in the Supplementary Material) was also performed. Additionally, the reference lists of identified studies and pertinent reviews on this topic were reviewed for any additional relevant studies.

2.3. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Included in this review were clinical studies in humans that provided data on implant failure rates for diabetic and non-diabetic patients treated with cylindrical, modern dental implants made from commercially pure titanium or its alloys. Since an individual cannot be randomized as diabetic or non-diabetic, non-randomized and retrospective clinical studies were also considered for inclusion.

Only studies involving diabetic patients under glycemic control were included. If glycemic control information was not available in the publication, it was obtained by contacting the study authors directly.

Excluded from this review were case reports, technical reports, animal studies, in vitro studies, and review papers. Additionally, studies focusing on mini-implants, zygomatic, orthodontic, zirconia, subperiosteal, or hollow implants were excluded.

3. Results

Detailed information on the 89 studies included, published between 2001 and 2023. These studies were primarily conducted at a single center ($n = 73$) or across multiple centers ($n = 16$). The studies comprised eight randomized clinical trials (RCTs), 11 prospective studies (without a pre-established control group), 15 prospective controlled clinical trials, and 55 retrospective observational studies. The countries with the highest frequency of studies included the USA ($n = 19$), Italy ($n = 13$), Spain ($n = 6$), and Brazil, Germany, and Belgium (five studies each), along with Austria, Portugal, and South Korea (four studies each), and Sweden ($n = 3$), among others.

The average follow-up period ($\pm$ standard deviation) for 72 studies was 38.8 ± 35.0 months, with a range from 3 to 194.3 months. Precise follow-up details were not available for the remaining 17 studies, which provided information like “patients were followed between 2006 and 2009” or “up to 48 months.”

The studies employed various loading protocols, with delayed loading being the most frequent (43 studies), followed by immediate loading (34 studies), early loading (4 studies), and no prosthetic loading (4 studies). This information was not reported in 23 studies. Some studies applied a single loading protocol for all implants, while others used a combination for different implants within the same study.

Among the studies, 63 included implants in both jaws, 13 focused only on maxillary implants, and 13 on mandibular implants. Eight studies specifically excluded smokers, and six did not provide information on smoking status within the patient cohort.

In total, 5,510 implants were placed in diabetic patients (with 394 failures), and 62,780 implants in non-diabetic patients (with 2,343 failures). The most frequently used implant brands were Nobel Biocare (Göteborg, Sweden) in 39 studies, Straumann (Basel, Switzerland) in 20 studies, and Astra Tech (Mölndal, Sweden) in 11 studies. The implant brand and/or system used was not specified in 12 studies.

A comparison of mean marginal bone loss (MBL) between diabetic and non-diabetic patients was available in 10 studies, of which nine also provided the standard deviation, necessary for conducting a meta-analysis of continuous variables.

4. Discussion

This systematic review aimed to compare clinical outcomes of dental implants in diabetic versus non-diabetic patients. While previous reviews have addressed this topic, they either did not include statistical analysis or were limited by a smaller number of clinical studies. This review, incorporating data from 89 studies, provides a broader scope and is the first to introduce several analyses: (a) a sub-analysis comparing implant failure rates between type 1 and type 2 diabetic patients; (b) subgroup analyses focusing separately on implants placed in maxillae and mandibles; (c) a meta-regression assessing the association between implant failure odds ratios for diabetic and non-diabetic individuals and follow-up duration; (d) a meta-analysis comparing MBL between diabetic and non-diabetic patients; and (e) a meta-regression examining the relationship between follow-up duration and MBL differences between diabetic and non-diabetic patients.

The findings from this review indicate that diabetic patients experience a significantly higher risk of dental implant failure and greater marginal bone loss compared to non-diabetic patients, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. These outcomes are largely attributed to the adverse effects of diabetes mellitus on various physiological processes in the body.

Diabetes mellitus negatively impacts bone metabolism and bone strength. Hyperglycemia, commonly resulting from inadequate glycemic control, can lower bone mineral density (BMD) and increase fracture risk by raising urinary calcium excretion and accumulating advanced glycation end products. This accumulation promotes inflammation, decreases insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1) levels, and creates a more acidic environment. IGF-1 plays a crucial role by enhancing bone matrix synthesis, promoting bone formation, and regulating osteoclastogenesis, which helps with bone resorption and remodeling. Clinical studies have shown that patients with type 1 diabetes have lower total body BMD compared to matched non-diabetic individuals.

Another complication of diabetes is delayed wound and bone healing. Dental implant placement involves controlled surgical intervention in the bone, which initiates healing processes beginning with blood clot formation, vascularization, and the migration of mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) from surrounding bone marrow. Under optimal conditions, MSCs differentiate into osteoblasts, leading to the formation of woven bone, which later compacts and remodels into mature bone. However, in diabetic patients, compromised bone cell metabolism and alterations in bone matrix properties hinder bone healing, reducing matrix strength and potentially jeopardizing implant osseointegration.

Conclusions

In summary, dental implants in diabetic patients exhibit a statistically significant higher risk of failure and increased marginal bone loss compared to implants in non-diabetic patients. Additionally, when comparing different types of diabetes mellitus, implants in patients with type I diabetes have a substantially higher risk of failure than those in patients with type II diabetes.

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